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DON TARKIBIDAGI GILIADIN OQSILLARINING POLIMORFIZMI

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Olingan natijalarga ko‘ra, bug‘doy navlarining genetik muhiti bug‘doy donining sifat belgilarini namoyon bo‘lishiga katta ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Odatda, bitta xromosomada yuzaga keluvchi eliminatsiya muhim ahamiyatga ega bo‘lgan genlarning yo‘qotilishini anglatmaydi, chunki bug‘doyda gomeologik genomlar mavjud hisoblanadi va yo‘qotilgan genetik materialning kompensatsiyalanishi gomeologlar hisobiga amalga oshadi.

Hozirgi vaqtda bug‘doy navlari va genotiplarini identifikatsiyalash va qayd qilish uchun dunyo miqyosida ilmiy markazlarda gliadinlarning elektrofez spektrlarini o‘rganishning alohida uslublari ishlab chiqilgan.

Shu bilan birgalikda, seleksiyada bug‘doy donining sifat darajasini aniqlash uchun yangi va barqaror tavsifdagi oqsil markerlarni aniqlash talab qilinadi. Bug‘doy doni tarkibida nisbatan batafsil o‘rganilgan oqsillar – bu, zahira oqsillari, ya‘ni gliadin va glyutenin hisoblanadi.

1-rasm. Gliadin oqsillarining elektroforetik spektri 4 ta zonaga ajralalishi.

Gliadin oqsillarining elektroforetik spektri 4 ta zonaga ajraladi, jumladan ular α -, β -, γ - va ω - zonalar bilan belgilangan. Bunda har bir zonada bir qator bandlar mavjudligi qayd qilinib, ular asosida nav ichidagi va navlararo farqlanishlar belgilanadi.

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2.2-rasm. “TURKISTON” navi lektroforegrammasi

Tajribalarimizda yumshoq bug‘doyning SHUKRONA, TURKISTON va YAKSART navlarini gliadin oqsillarini elektroforetik spektridagi bandlar soni, jadalligi, minor, o‘rtacha faol yoki major guruhlarga ajratgan holda tahlil qilindi. Morfologik belgilari bo‘yicha taxlil qilinib, alohida nav namunasi sifatida ajratilib olingan 3 ta navning elektroforetik spektrlari nazorat sifatida olingan Bezostaya-1 navining elektroforetik spektriga solishtirma holda tahlil qilinganda bir biridan farq qiluvchi 27 xil spektr namoyon bo‘ldi. Bunda o‘rganilgan nav namunalarning har biridan 100 tadan doni tahlil qilinganda 2 ta navda elektroforetik spektrlari bir xil ekanligi kuzatilib, ular gliadin oqsillari spektri bo‘yicha gomogen ekanligi aniqlandi.

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